

LINGUOCULTURAL INTERPRETATION OF MYTHOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE TRANSLATION OF THE EPIC “ALPOMISH”

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the linguocultural features of mythological units found in the translation of the epic “Alpomish” and the ways they are rendered into English. The study examines the semantic and connotative characteristics of such Arabic-Islamic mythological units as “Lot,” “Manot,” “dev,” and “pari,” as well as the ethnographic unit “shopar.” Comparative-typological, semantic, and linguocultural methods of analysis were employed in the research.

Keywords: *mythological unit, linguoculture, lacuna, folklore translation, semantic transformation, “Alpomish,” denotative meaning, connotative meaning.*

INTRODUCTION

Year by year, relations between our country and other nations of the world are developing, which accelerates the process of integration. In the process of exchanging information with representatives of different countries, issues such as correctly expressing the national-cultural specificity of communication, verbal and non-verbal means used in intercultural communication, the representation of reality in human consciousness, people’s lifestyle, and national identity in a foreign language demonstrate the growing relevance of learning foreign languages (Shomuratova I., 2024). Mythological units occurring in folklore works constitute an important linguocultural layer reflecting the ancient worldview, religious beliefs, and cultural memory of a people. Especially in epic works such as the epic *Alpomish*, mythologemes function as expressions of national thinking, archaic perceptions, and religious-cultural views (Jirmunsky, 1974; Mirzaev, 1968). The epic *Alpomish* stands as one of the most significant examples of Turkic epic thought, giving vivid artistic

expression to heroism, tribal structure, ceremonial practice, and social relations. (Shomuratova I., 2026)

In the process of translating such units into another language, the translator should convey not only the lexical meaning but also the connotative, historical, and cultural load of the unit (Nida and Taber, 1969). As noted by Ozoda Ruzmetova, words in language resemble one another, and their meanings change according to different contexts of usage (Ruzmetova O., 2023).

Arabic-Islamic mythological units such as “Lot,” “Manot,” “dev,” and “pari” are actively used in Uzbek folklore and intensify the artistic and aesthetic expressiveness of epic narration. Indeed, any translator engaged in rendering the masterpieces of Uzbek classical literature into another language should have a profound understanding of the traditions of Eastern literary culture and reproduce not only the semantic and conceptual essence of the original text but also preserve its musical harmony and aesthetic expressiveness in the target language (Otajonova L., 2023). These mythological images enrich the semantic and linguocultural layer of folklore texts by embodying ancient religious beliefs, mythopoetic thinking, and collective cultural memory. In particular, the units “Lot” and “Manot” express historical and mythological concepts related to pre-Islamic Arab beliefs, whereas the images of “dev” and “pari” represent opposing poetic concepts such as good and evil, beauty and horror in Eastern folklore. The study of acquired words has its own tradition (Divanova M., 2023).

Therefore, such units function not merely as lexical devices but as linguocultural markers reflecting the mentality, worldview, and cultural identity of a particular people. Lacunae, rather than signifying deficits or inadequacies in language systems, underscore the profound diversity, cultural specificity, and epistemological richness inherent in human communication and thought (Shomuratova I., 2025). It is a person’s ability to communicate successfully, based on their level of knowledge of their own language and linguistic norms, as well as their ability to understand a wide variety of texts. (Sabirova B., 2025)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed comparative-typological, semantic, and linguocultural methods of analysis. The Uzbek text of the epic “Alpomish” and its English translation were comparatively examined. The denotative and connotative meanings of mythological units were analyzed on the basis of lexicographic sources and folklore dictionaries. Translation transformations such as generalization, semantic adaptation, interpretative translation, and equivalent substitution (Newmark, 1988) were identified and scientifically interpreted.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The units “Lot” and “Manot” found in the epic “Alpomish” possess special linguocultural significance as ancient religious concepts related to Arabic-Islamic mythology. These mythologemes are closely connected with the beliefs, idolatrous traditions, and mythological thinking of pre-Islamic Arab society and create a historical-cultural coloring within the folklore text. These units are used not simply as religious names but as symbolic expressions of abandoning old beliefs and transitioning toward Islamic consciousness.

Translating such mythological units into another language constitutes one of the most complex problems in translation studies. Depending on the circumstances or on the conditions in which the speech act is committed, it can either achieve the intended goal and thus be successful, or fail to do so (Abidova R, 2023). Since the mythologemes “Lot” and “Manot” contain not only denotative meaning but also strong connotative, religious, and historical components, failure to preserve their cultural semantics may significantly weaken the national spirit and mythopoetic features of the text.

The following line occurs in the epic: “Qorajon, sen lot-manotdan yuz o‘girib, islomning diniga kirib...” (Alpomish, 1998, 139) These units refer to deities worshipped by ancient Arabs before Islam. As religious-mythological concepts, “Lot” and “Manot” possess not only denotative but also strong connotative meanings. Since there is no complete equivalent for pre-Islamic Arab mythological concepts in English, the translator is compelled to apply various transformational methods, including transliteration, generalization, interpretative translation, and semantic adaptation. In the English translation these units are rendered as:

“So, you're no heathen now, but a Mussulman...”(Ma'murov K, Alpomish, 66,2023)

Here, the translator replaces the concrete mythological names with the generalized concept “heathen.” As a result, although the denotative meaning is partially preserved, the historical and religious coloring specific to “Lot” and “Manot” disappears. The translation employs the transformation of generalization (Newmark, 1988). Consequently, the intertextual layer connected with Arab mythology is significantly simplified in the English version, leading to a reduction of national-cultural information. (Otajanova L., Yuldashev D.,2023).

The unit “shopar” found in the language of the epic “Alpomish” represents an example of ethnographic vocabulary associated with the national lifestyle, horse-breeding culture, and epic thinking of the Uzbek people. It generally refers to the long mane of a horse or a wing-like fluttering part and serves to express the hero's power, dynamism, and movement in poetic form.

In the line: “Endi ketdim shoparlarim yoyilib” (Alpomish, 1998,144)

the word “shopar” denotes the long mane or wing-like fluttering part of a horse (Madvaliyev, 2008). In epic poetics, this unit symbolizes movement, strength, and grandeur.

In translation, however, it is rendered as: “He spread his wings, and began to soar.” (Ma'murov K, Alpomish, 69,2023)

Here, “shopar” is translated interpretatively through the word “wings” (Newmark, 1988). In order to make the image understandable for the English reader, the translator applies metaphorical adaptation (Nida and Taber, 1969). Nevertheless, the national-poetic semantics specifically connected with the horse image are lost. Thus, although functional equivalence is preserved, the ethnographic component is not fully reflected (Vlakhov and Florin, 1980).

The units “dev” and “pari” occurring in the epic “Alpomish” are among the most ancient and active mythopoetic images of Eastern mythology and oral folklore. These mythologemes reflect archaic perceptions, mythological ideas about good and evil, and fantastic imagination. The image of “dev” symbolizes brutality and evil, whereas “pari” symbolizes beauty, divine light, purity, and goodness.

In the following line: “Yo asar qildimi dev bilan pari?” (Alpomish, 1998,151)

“dev” represents evil and immense power, while “pari” symbolizes beauty and divinity in Eastern mythology. This antonymic mythological pair creates a poetic contrast characteristic of Eastern folklore (Mirzaev, 1977).

In translation, the following variant is used: “Why do sprites confuse you, and lead you afar?” (Ma'murov K, Alpomish, 76,2023)

Here, both “dev” and “pari” are generalized into the single lexical unit “sprites” (Vlakhov & Florin, 1980). As a result, the opposing semantic nature of the images disappears. Although the translator attempts to preserve the overall mythological atmosphere of the text, the individual national-cultural features of the mythologemes are not fully conveyed in English. In this case, semantic neutralization and generalization are observed (Newmark, 1988).

The analysis demonstrates that translating mythological units in folklore is a highly complex linguocultural process (Venuti, 1995). Translators often resort to generalization or interpretative translation to ensure comprehensibility for the target reader (Nida and Taber, 1969). However, such approaches may lead to the weakening of national coloring. The translation of details concerning each character's appearance is a process that requires particular attention in order to reconstruct a realistic representation of the luxurious lifestyle of palace elites as reflected through clothing and to convey the image and characterization of historical figures that embody the distinctive historical and national identity represented in the historical work.(Otajonova L.2023/7)

CONCLUSION

The analysis revealed that translating mythological units in the epic “Alpomish” into English is a complex linguocultural and translational process. Mythologemes such as “Lot,” “Manot,” “dev,” and “pari,” as well as ethnographic units like “shopar,” embody the historical memory, religious beliefs, and mythopoetic thinking of the people; therefore, simple lexical equivalence is insufficient in their translation. The research established that

the English translation mainly employs strategies such as generalization, interpretative translation, semantic adaptation, and functional equivalence.

The results indicate that although the general meaning of the text is preserved in some cases, the national-cultural, historical, and poetic features of mythological units are partially lost. In particular, rendering “Lot” and “Manot” through the generalized concept “heathen” weakens the historical-mythological coloring. Likewise, conveying “dev” and “pari” through the single lexeme “sprites” diminishes the poetic contrast characteristic of Eastern mythology. Although translating “shopar” as “wings” partially preserves the poetic spirit of the text, the ethnographic semantics related to horse-breeding culture are not fully reflected.

Therefore, in translating mythological and linguocultural units in folklore, it is important to preserve not only the denotative meaning but also the connotative, historical, and cultural layers of the unit. Thus, the use of transliteration, explanatory translation, and linguocultural commentary may contribute to conveying the national spirit of folklore works more fully.

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